

EVALUATION & IMPACT MEASUREMENT

Who? Audience:
Program
Managers, Grant
Administrators,
Funders

Why? Measuring Engagement Matters

Tracking engagement effectiveness helps improve strategies, secure funding, and demonstrate impact.

Key Metrics for Success

Process Metrics

Number of participants, meeting attendance, engagement activities.

Outcome Metrics

Behavior change, policy shifts, increased community trust.

Equity Indicators

Representation of marginalized voices in decision-making.

Evaluation Methods

Qualitative Approaches

Conduct focus groups, interviews, and case studies.

Quantitative Data

Track survey responses, participation rates, and engagement levels.

Community-Led Assessment

Involve community members in defining success metrics.

ACTION STEPS

- Define clear goals and success indicators.
- Utilize both qualitative and quantitative evaluation tools.
- Share findings with stakeholders and adapt strategies accordingly.
- See chapter 8: Program Evaluation, see chapter 9: Positioned for Sustainability